

DELIVERABLE

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Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan including graphic design guidelines (release 2)

D6.3

Version 1.2

Authors:

Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED)
Raffaella Santucci (QED)

Contributors:

David Nathaniel Winkler (QED)

Reviewers:

Vincenzo Grillo (CNR)
Stefano Frabboni (UNIMORE)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

«In the vanguard, beyond the borders of knowledge,
science becomes even more beautiful»
Carlo Rovelli

This Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan provides an update of the dissemination strategy, activities, and materials that Q-SORT intends to use over the lifetime of the Project, with the goal of making it as visible as possible and of disseminating the Project's results as widely as possible.

The dissemination and engagement activities are targeted to reach:

- the scientific research community, including national research agencies
- science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science
- audiences from projects similar to Q-SORT
- high-school students
- policy-group members
- private-enterprise scientists and managers.

The Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan identifies the methods to be employed to reach each of these target groups, how to tune the messages accordingly, and the expected outcome of those activities.

Central to the identity and presence of Q-SORT is the Project Website, whose role is described in this document and whose design is discussed in more detail in D6.1 Q-SORT Project Website.

In addition, the current document describes how Q-SORT intends to capitalise on the potential of social media (SM) for informing and spreading awareness on the project, as well as engaging with a wider audience.

Finally, a series of Conferences, Webinars, Science Bashes will also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process, and, together with the Website and SM profiles, will ensure that the results will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

This document serves as an easy-to-use internal guide for the project partners. In addition, it describes the dissemination methodologies and activities to be carried out by partners in the project and how these processes will be monitored.

A further aim of this document is to improve, streamline, and standardise the procedures concerning the project's dissemination activities and to provide Q-SORT partners with branding guidelines to be adopted. The standardisation of procedures will also help the project management in monitoring and reporting activities and outcomes.

We acknowledge that the present document is built on the successful dissemination experiences and strategies of previous European projects such as [Linked Heritage](#) and [EAGLE](#).

NOTE FOR THE RESUBMISSION - V1.2

Broadly speaking, we take the Project Review very seriously, which is why we have implemented, insofar as possible, all the desiderata expressed in the Review Letter and Review Report. Nevertheless, we have a few unavoidable and important counterclaims to make to some of the methodological issues that have been raised.

To note:

- The Letter and Report demand more digested and curated scientific content be given out¹ through the website as well as social media. We do understand the need for a certain level of introductory text in order to provide context as well as links to other more in-depth resources. However, we also have to point out that reliance on public understanding of science (PUS) rather than on awareness and engagement (PAWS and PEST respectively) reflects an out-of-date paradigm for science communication, based on the so-called “information-deficit model”. A growing body of studies attests instead that approaches based on the “low-information rationality” theory, and therefore relying mostly on PAWS and PEST, tend to be more effective. This is also in agreement with our experience of more than 20 years in communication and science communication.

The deliberate choice of PAWS over PUS on our part during the first year is why the main aim of Dissemination and Engagement during this period has been to foster awareness of the Project’s existence - by devising a strong brand identity for Q-SORT and then ‘pushing’ it over social media (SM). To put it another way, staking a presence is a necessary prerequisite for being able to effectively deliver complex content. This strategy was already present in the Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan as originally submitted: the “Raise awareness, Engage, Communicate” actions (as stated in **4.3.1 Summary of channels/actions**) were always intended to be sequential, as there cannot be effective communication of scientific content without having previously ensured awareness and engagement.

Low-information rationality, and again a growing number of studies as well as consensus amongst communication experts, is also behind our contention that the most effective communication on SM is done via ‘immediate’ content such as images and video, rather than through text, which anyway should be kept very short. This is all the more true if such text is trying to explain very advanced science.

As requested by the Review, we are implementing a gradual shift in the emphasis of communication, entailing more scientific textual content. This was already foreseen in the future SM publishing plans for the years after the first one.

- The Letter and Report demand more information about the Project be given out². We have to point out that this was already in the plans from the beginning, as the originally-submitted version of the Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan clearly stated: “Messages will vary through the lifetime of the Project. In the initial phases, dissemination is more focused on encouraging awareness of the

¹ “So far, communication to the non-expert was mainly through ‘images’. The focus should gradually tend to explain the content”
“So far, communication to the non-expert was mainly through visual effects. The focus should gradually tend to explain the content”
“Nevertheless, it would be useful for wider audience, if the resumé of the presentation will be made; such a comprehensible text will offer a better understanding of the topics.”

² “So far, on the website only the PI is mentioned in the participation section. An overview of the publications resulting from the project should be included together with a link where the publications can be downloaded. The Press Corner should be populated with direct references to [...]”

“The website should reflect the progress of the project by posting these scientific achievements, events, publications, links to training webinars, etc. Open access data could also be posted on the website.”

“Also links to the webinars can be given in the Q-SORT website”

“the website should reflect the progress of the project”

“open access data (if available) could be posted on the website”

project, while during the last year the Project will focus on promoting its major achievements.” By complying with the Review request, we are simply anticipating what was already in the plans.

The reason behind the planned shift of focus as originally stated by us is actually very simple: because of the way the scientific work is organised throughout the Project, the first half of the Project is devoted to lengthy testing and trial-and-error, and therefore much less newsworthy.

- Regarding requests on the Project Website³, while we understand the convenience of being able to find all or most of the communication work done in one place, such an approach necessarily negates many of the advantages that SM bring: as explained in the originally-submitted version of the Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan (**Social Networks** paragraph within chapter **4.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels**), as well as during the WP6 Review Presentation and in the re-submitted Project Website and Logo deliverables, effective communication generates traffic on the various SM, with the aim of funnelling it to the Website. So, whilst the Website can certainly work as a showcase for the project, it cannot do so on its own - the legwork for communication to the general public is done on SNs. Any notion of establishing a project portal of sorts that people will access directly and use, as it was the case in the Nineties for instance, is a recipe for very low impact: people today either browse social media, or directly access only those very-high-PageRank websites that provide one or more useful services; such is not the case for the Q-SORT website - unless one is a journalist looking for the press kit, or a scientist looking for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.
- We do understand the need to have a Project Website that provides an at-a-glance overview of everything - this is especially useful for quickly presenting Q-SORT to other institutions and, in general, to people who have little time. We have thus enriched and expanded the Project Website with new information as per the Review Report requests⁴. These changes are detailed in D6.5.

Having said this, for the reasons expounded above in this chapter, in our opinion even a simple ‘showcase’ Project Website would have been appropriate, as the bulk of online communication and outreach is done via SM, using content that is produced specifically for SM. This is how the highest number of people can be reached. This is the best value for money in terms of engaging with the general public. Spending effort populating the Q-SORT webpages and increasing the number of subpages with curated content, whilst laudable, is therefore not the best use of project resources in this respect.

In short, we are certainly thankful for the feedback provided by the Review, which we have incorporated in the revised deliverables and Website. However, we must also recall that the excellent communication work that was carried out during the First Year, on time and within budget, completely fulfilled all the project goals and metrics as laid down in the Workplan. We stand behind our well-structured Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan, which now also includes a Twitter profile, as requested⁵, and remain convinced that, given the project goals, we have thus far provided the best use of resources and best value for money.

³ See previous two notes, particularly footnote no. 2.

⁴ See previous notes.

⁵ “The Consortium is advised to start communication on Tweeter”

STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document features 6 chapters.

Chapter 1, the Introduction, provides a brief overview of the deliverable's objectives.

Chapter 2 describes the goals that Q-SORT intends to reach through its dissemination, communication and engagement activities as described in the DoW.

Chapter 3 describes the target audience to be reached. Q-SORT addresses the research community, the general public, the contributing community (i.e. academia, private sector), government and policy bodies.

Chapter 4 analyses the variety of dissemination, communication and engagement methods to be adopted with the goal of disseminating and communicating outcomes and results.

Chapter 5 describes how the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities will be continuously evaluated and according to which criteria.

Chapter 6 briefly summarises this report.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the Q-SORT project the dissemination and public engagement plan concerns:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Coordination/admin staff
- Web site managers

with a particular emphasis on the staff that is responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, since this is a public document and is available on the Project Website, the plan will be accessible by external parties interested in the dissemination plan of the Q-SORT project.

This deliverable aims to function as an easy-to-use internal guide for the Q-SORT network.

It describes all the elements required for the effective execution of the Q-SORT Dissemination and Public Engagement, i.e.:

1. the objectives the project intends to reach through its dissemination activities;
2. the target audiences, describing their interests and characteristics;
3. the methods and the timetable of the results' dissemination to the target audiences;
4. the branding/graphic design guidelines.

This deliverable has been updated in accordance with the project's evolving needs, activities, and achievements.

2 WHY AND WHAT – GOALS

The aim of Q-SORT's dissemination and public engagement is to spread awareness of concepts, worldviews, and notions generated by the science behind the project. It will do so by broadcasting exciting, meaningful 'information nuggets' online through a variety of strategies, as well as by involving citizens in participatory events (and/or their online version) pertaining to the world of science and science culture. In this effort, Q-SORT will also take advantage of the combined experience and capacity of its Consortium members.

Q-SORT aims to achieve the following objectives through its dissemination and public engagement activities:

1. To spread knowledge of the Project amongst non-specialists through communication and engagement activities. This has the twin goals of spreading knowledge and awareness about science, as well as about how the EU-funded world-class research.
2. To spread knowledge of the Project amongst other scientists through dissemination, so as to foster future uptake of resulting sorter-related techniques and technologies.
3. To promote science vocation among young people through communication and engagement.
4. To foster through dissemination the enlargement of Q-SORT's scientific network, for further future collaborations.
5. To seek to meaningfully inform relevant policy-group members and decision makers in public institutions devoted to science funding.
6. To make European enterprises aware of the opportunities afforded by EC R&I project.

Through this Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan, WP6 intends to facilitate the achievement of the above-mentioned goals, including all the while the contributions of all Q-SORT partners and WP Leaders.

Q-SORT overall dissemination and engagement ethos emphasises inclusiveness. This results in a fundamentally grassroots approach to science communication and in the involvement of civil society organisations such as the Wikimedia Foundation. The overall aim is to reverse the usually adopted strategies by embracing an inductive rather than a deductive approach to the public understanding of science. Therefore, the focus tends to be, rather than on 'science made understandable to people', on 'people made to participate in science initiatives'. Gender issues in science will be treated with particular attention.

All dissemination and public engagement activities will be conducted under the coordination of the partner QED, which will ensure the delivery of a consistent message from the Project to the 'outer world'.

3 WHO – THE Q-SORT TARGET AUDIENCE

The various target groups for Q-SORT were determined based on the overall goals of dissemination and engagement. In decreasing order of importance, and of overall expected reach, they are: the research community, science enthusiasts and the curious, audiences from Q-SORT ‘sister’ projects, high-school students, policy-group members, private-enterprise scientists and managers, and also the general public. Within each of these demographics, special consideration will be given -within the constraints of Q-SORT’s limited funding for outreach- to the so-called ‘silent stakeholders’, i.e. disadvantaged or minority categories such as women, the elderly, the poor.

The above target audiences are made up of either specialists (i.e. scientists) or non-specialists. Reaching specialists is important for the uptake of the science and technology developed in Q-SORT. Reaching non-specialists is important as a cultural mission in general, but also to spread awareness about cutting-edge research, its importance, and how adequately the EU is funding it.

3.1 The research community

This community is represented by researchers and experts working in the fields of nanoscience, electron microscopy, quantum optics, and solid-state physics, biochemistry, biology in general - but also less immediately-related disciplines such as accelerator physics and quantum computing. All these scientists can potentially benefit from the results of the project, either from the application of the sorter in their respective disciplines or from the adoption of beam-shaping techniques developed for Q-SORT. We also consider national groups, European and international organisations (such as the European Microscopy Society) to be part of this community.

3.1.1 National research-agency scientists

A significant subset of the research community, this large and diverse group can be easily reached through specialised channels (e.g. mailing lists) and may benefit from Q-SORT scientific results by reusing them at a national level - e.g. by adopting sorter-related technologies, theory, and practices. Considering that several partners are also involved in European projects dealing with e-infrastructures, the transparent sharing of information relating to Q-SORT open data serves to inform these groups as well as e-infrastructure providers and managers. Also, open data made available by Q-SORT might possibly find use as training datasets for the machine learning community.

3.2 Science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science

Citizens who have an interest in science, from different countries and from a wide demographics, are our prime non-specialist target, as they are easier to reach -thanks to already-existing communities and groups of interest- and much more likely to appreciate Q-SORT’s scientific and aesthetic aspects. It is important to reach this large group both as a cultural mission as well as to inform taxpayers on how public moneys are being invested.

Besides a variety of online posts and initiatives (see Section 4), events targeted to reach this demographic, such as the Q-SORT Science Bash, will take place in new, unusual locations generally not taken into consideration for the public understanding of science; these might include pubs, clubs, cafés; but also music and art festivals happening in the same city. The choice of these new locations aims to extend the reach of Q-SORT to those who are interested in science but generally don’t frequent traditional venues. This also reflects our overall preoccupation to try to reach the so-called ‘silent stakeholders’, i.e. under-represented portions of the public such as women, the elderly, the poorer, recent immigrants. Content-wise, references to local/regional conditions will be featured whenever possible, leveraging Q-SORT partners’ existing connections to local territories. Unfortunately, Q-SORT’s limited budget allows just for a handful of live events, but these will be highly targeted and their success will serve as a metrics for future

such like initiatives in EC projects. Regular mini-events for this demographic will also comprise Wikimedia Edit-a-thons.

3.3 Audiences from Q-SORT ‘sister’ projects

Q-SORT shares similar target audiences with other quantum technology and electron microscopy projects. Also, other FET projects share similar non-specialist target audiences with Q-SORT.

Outreach synergies with these projects hold the potential for a multiplier effect. Collaboration with sister projects is also important in order to optimise effort and avoid duplication of messages. The projects that could benefit from dissemination/engagement synergies with Q-SORT are listed in Section 4.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels.

3.4 High-school students

This demographics is important in general because it represents the citizens of tomorrow. It is also strategically important to reach in order to begin to address the vocational crisis in science subjects that is being felt in some EU countries. The low proportion of students and graduates in science and technology is, in fact, a concern for future innovation capacity in the EU. Putting high-school students in touch with the beauty and the challenges of cutting-edge research in science is one of Q-SORT aims. Providing informal science education by illustrating key concepts related to Q-SORT is another. Since high-school students are highly active on social networks, these will be our primary conduit.

3.5 Policy-group members

This target group includes policy makers at the national and European levels.

At the European Level the target is mainly represented by the Member States and by Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission which defines and implements European Research and Innovation (R&I) policy with a view to achieving the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy and its key flagship initiative, the Innovation Union. Communication with this group is important in order to spread awareness of recent scientific developments as well as to propose best practices and improvements in how resources for R&I are invested.

Dissemination targeted to these users is crucial for the sustainability of the Project. Disseminating Q-SORT results among government ministries and agencies, which control or lobby for funding research institutions of all sorts, is valuable in order for the Q-SORT partners to be supported in the future at the national government level. Communication towards this group is fundamental to ensure a more adequate level of national funding for fundamental research, which, with a few exceptions, is not funded by the EU. This is of paramount importance in order to keep alive the research ecosystem.

3.6 Private-enterprise scientists and managers

It is important to target this group so that interested parties become aware of the opportunities provided by the FET programme for the private sector. Two enterprises, FEI/Thermo Fisher (a technology company) and QED (a media production company) are already part of the Q-SORT consortium and can provide insights.

3.7 Notes on the general public

The focus of Q-SORT dissemination and engagement is to increase awareness among selected stakeholders, so as to maximise the return on the investment made on these activities. However, insofar as possible given the limited resources allotted to WP6, we want to also try to address the wider public. Whilst it

is generally considered futile to try to address a generalist audience without massive communication resources, we will nevertheless be taking a number of steps so as to ensure that our activities do not alienate a mass audience. Therefore, as a general principle, we will:

- employ friendly, inclusive, and non intimidating language
- seek to post high-quality, fresh content with far-reaching appeal
- include hashtags and channels that might help us reach new audiences
- strive to hold engagement events in new, non-intimidating locations such as pubs and cafès.

The latter will allow Q-SORT to reach new audiences that tend to avoid the more traditional spaces that are generally being used to communicate science.

3.8 General overview of target groups and corresponding messages

The following table summarises the type of audience, the messages to be communicated, the foreseen impact, and the partners' involvement.

AUDIENCE	MESSAGE TO BE COMMUNICATED ⁶	MAIN IMPACT	Q-SORT ACTORS INVOLVED
The research community	New sorter-related tools, techniques, theory (for beam-shaping or sorting) are available or are being developed with potential applications <i>in your domain</i> #CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch [other more specific hashtags will also be used, such as #Sorter, #BeamShaping, etc.]	National, European, International	All partners, WP Leaders and EAB
National research-agency scientists	New sorter-related tools, techniques, theory (for beam-shaping or sorting) are available or are being developed with potential applications <i>in your domain</i> #CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch [other more specific hashtags will also be used, such as #Sorter, #BeamShaping, etc.]	National, European, International	All partners
Science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science	Science is beautiful Research is important The EU invests in research #ScienceIsCool #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of QED

⁶ Hashtags are used here for the sake of conciseness

	#EUfundsResearch #FundResearchForAbetterWorld		
Audiences from Q-SORT 'sister' projects	#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #SciencelsCool #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European, International	All partners, but mainly WP leaders
High school students	#SciencelsCool #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European	All partners
Policy groups, agencies and governments	Make more regular funding available for fundamental research at the national level Ask for increased R&I budget at EU level #MakingTheFutureHappenNow #MoreWomenGirlsInSTEM #FundResearchForAbetterWorld #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch	National, European, International	All partners
Private-enterprise scientists and managers	EU funding is available for enterprises that want to do research #EUhelpsEnterprises #EUfundsResearch #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European	All partners
General Public	#SciencelsCool #EUfundsResearch #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of QED

4 HOW - METHODOLOGY

The Q-SORT project makes use of a variety of dissemination and public engagement methods.

As a general remark, given the limited budget that EC projects are able to allot to Dissemination efforts, promotion of Q-SORT through traditional mass media is not economically viable, in the sense that advertising is too expensive for adequately promoting Q-SORT. On the other hand, online communication, especially through social media, is much cheaper and can be tailored with great precision to very specific groups - defined by specific interests, age range, geographic location. It therefore provides a truly optimal return on investment, which is why it will be used extensively for Q-SORT.

Messages will vary through the lifetime of the Project. In the initial phases, dissemination is more focused on encouraging awareness of the project, while during the last year the Project will focus on promoting its major achievements.

Q-SORT aims to expand the capacity of European and national science actors to effect better societal engagement. Q-SORT embraces the PE2020 and ENGAGE2020 outcomes and aims to support a shift towards a more dynamic relationship between science and society. The project aims to achieve this objective by using and exploring recent cutting-edge PE innovation practices (see Events in Section 4.3) within this composite and multifaceted field.

Inclusive, participatory events such as the Wiki Edit-a-thons and the Science Bashes, as well as the special attention paid to gender issues and minority stakeholders, also make Q-SORT RRI-compliant. Q-SORT fully shares the RRI aim of engaging society in open science and innovation.

Finally, compliance with Open Science and Open Innovation EC policies is ensured by the project-specific Open Data Management Plan. The latter, which was due at M6, has been dealt with according to the Pilot on Open Research Data Guidelines.

The following paragraphs briefly summarise our approach.

4.1 Q-SORT Branding Guidelines

When we say the 'branding guidelines' of the project, we mean a set of elements and guidelines that should characterise the institutional communication of the project in order to simplify and make recognisable our communication activities (project visual identity, in short, see also *D6.1 Q-SORT Project Website*).

Given the particular nature of the Q-SORT content, we feel it is important to pay attention to our communications to both specialised audiences and external, non-specialised audiences. In particular, the development of the following elements has been considered for Q-SORT's branding efforts:

1. Basic elements (see also: D6.1 Q-SORT Project Website)

- Brand Logo
- Branding architecture, meaning a cohesive system of typographical rules, visual relations and hierarchies between the brand-logo and the (typo)graphical elements connectable to it (e.g. the Q-SORT brand-logotype and event titles)

2. Web (see also: D6.1 Q-SORT Project Website)

Templates for the web pages (that are compatible with the CMS of the portal), in particular:

- main portal page;
- general page template;
- events pages template; news template, partners' page template;
- contacts page template / Who We Are, etc.

3. Printed material

- Three-sided A4 foldable Project brochure;
- Q-SORT branded tote bag;
- A2 Project Conference poster;
- Project vinyl banner;
- Q-SORT conferences' Book of Abstracts.

4. Ready-to-use layouts

- Electronic communication documents (e.g. outreach toolkits);
- PowerPoint/Keynote for presentations;
- A4 template for Q-SORT-headed paper for invitations and courteous communications;
- Template for Conference Participation Certificates.

Figure 1 Q-SORT Slides Template – Snapshot

4.2 Adjusting the language according to the target audience

The Q-SORT project aims to develop knowledge and tools that can be technically complex and challenging. The language we use in order to communicate these ideas is therefore critical. Its importance cannot be underestimated, for it can make the difference between accepting or dismissing important concepts.

Therefore, the same messages, when targeted at different audiences, often need to be expressed in different ways: the language used must become more or less technical according to the intended audience it is addressing. For example, writing a paper for a scientific journal demands a more technical language, facilitating the reading with images, schemas, and tables. On the other hand, a short paper for the institution’s newsletter or website needs to be expressed in non-technical terms using language that the audience is familiar with. Writing for the Web in general needs to present ideas clearly, and concisely. Also, crucially, given the Project’s remit to spread the use of the sorter to different scientific domains, there is a need to communicate complex concepts to other scientists from different fields (e.g. communicating physics to biologists). This is an intermediate, interdisciplinary level of communication.

Therefore, Q-SORT can be said to have, in general, at least three distinct levels of communication: highly specialistic, interdisciplinary, general public.

Specialistic communication is taken care of by the peer-reviewed articles that the Project begets, whose manuscripts are also Project Deliverables.

On the other hand, both dedicated Wikipedia articles (see 4.3 below) and Interdisciplinary Webinars (as per WP3) were conceived as tools for the communication of information at all three different levels, with a particular emphasis on the latter two. Wikipedia articles in particular can function as an interactive online

lexicon that is particularly flexible and user-friendly, and which moreover is available to anyone. This is why we decided to invest time and resources in the Wiki Edit-a-thons.

4.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels

In this section we summarise the main conduits through which the Project will reach its intended target groups.

- **Q-SORT Project Website**

The [Q-SORT website](#) has already been described in *D6.1 Q-SORT Project Website*, which illustrates the its aims, the users that it targets, the adopted CMS, the structure of the public and reserved areas, the implementation work, services, editorial board, and the tools for monitoring.

The Q-SORT website is the hub of the dissemination and communication strategy of Q-SORT. It facilitates the management of the **community** created around the project activities. The members of the community will be strongly encouraged to participate, as most of the communication will occur online.

The Website presents the project to all target audiences and gives detailed, tailored information to stakeholders and journalists on project progress, activities, and results (among other things). The aim is to publish news, data, and other relevant project deliverables in a way that can be useful to other researchers and potential business partners.

The website also features (or will feature):

- a **dedicated News section for the public at large**, in which project activities are presented in a non-technical way; this section may also include photos and short videos documenting what is going on;
- attached social media groups (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter);
- a **Reserved Area** – which only partners can access – for the exchange of working documents;

Figure 2 The Q-SORT Website - Snapshot of special pink version of the Project landing webpage used for the International Day of Women in Science

- a **“Meet Your Scientist” section**: this area will provide highlights of Q-SORT results and insights into scientists’ lives and activities, presented as narratives centered on a different scientist each time.

Users visiting the Website will thus be able to:

- ★ browse Project News
- ★ view the Project Video
- ★ download public files such as the latest Press Release and Outreach Toolkit, as well as published articles and public deliverables
- ★ replay the Interdisciplinary Webinars
- ★ access further reading about the science behind the project (Meet Your Scientist, links to online resources, etc.)
- ★ contact Q-SORT scientists to ask questions
- ★ browse Q-SORT past and upcoming Events
- ★ browse short video testimonials and beautiful TEM images
- ★ upload and download work files in the password-protected Reserved Area

- **Partner institutions’ websites**

Partners are encouraged to disseminate Q-SORT activities and outcomes on their own institutional websites, periodically updating news, and links to relevant documentation. Partners will be asked to put links to the the Q-SORT Website on their institutional websites, so as to increase its Google PageRank.

Figure 3 The Q-SORT Twitter Page – snapshot

- **Online fast communication**

Partners are encouraged to promote Q-SORT activities and outcomes on their institutional mailing lists, newsletters/e-bulletins, and social media channels.

- **Social Networks**

The adoption of social network profiles allows the Project to promote visibility of the Q-SORT Website content and help spread online word-of-mouth about the research progress and wealth of materials available.

To this end, based on our target demographics, we activated Q-SORT profiles on the main Social Networks. We recently re-assessed SN presence and activities based on metrics as well as on a survey which was circulated amongst TEM and quantum optics scientists, which confirmed the importance of LinkedIn as a platform for reaching through to scientists. Here are the corresponding links:

Facebook

<https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/>

LinkedIn

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/quantum-sorter/>

Twitter

<https://twitter.com/quantumsorter>

Social Networks are a crucial tool for communicating the project and building a community of interested users around it.

Highly engaging content -in the form of science news, beautiful images, webinars and short videos, pregnant quotes, video testimonials, etc.- are being regularly posted and promoted. Relevant existing communities, groups, and pages will be exploited to this end. A-B testing of Facebook posts will be employed systematically, taking advantage of the various metrics provided by the platform.

It is important to realise that SNs are media channels in their own right and, as such, need a clear editorial guideline and regular updates backed by a publishing plan drafted every three months. To this end, social network posts for Q-SORT are created so as to conform to either one of the following categories:

1) General science posts

General-interest quirky science posts, pertaining mostly to the physical sciences and with particular emphasis to TEM. These can also be reposts of existing excellent articles, with which we share the same target audience.

2) Q-SORT news and EC news

This are Q-SORT news proper: papers published, prizes, events, etc. EC news on R&I are part of this category.

3) Testimonials from researchers

These are short videos and images related to Q-SORT, chronicling work through personal perspective/updates, and thus bringing out the 'human element' behind scientific research.

4) Basic science terms explained

These are short posts on basic Q-SORT science concepts, explained by specialists: guest posts, didactic but easy, on basic subjects such as what is the superposition of states, what is a SEM, what is coherence, etc.

5) Brilliant TEM images

Large, beautiful TEM images with a short caption explaining what they depict.

6) Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (see WP3)

Available to anyone although aimed chiefly at an audience of scientists from other disciplines (=biochemists, physicists from outside the TEM world), these are broadcast live over Facebook.

Figure 4 The Q-SORT Facebook Page – Snapshot

- **Wikimedia**

Regular Wiki Edit-a-thons are being organised with the aim of editing and improving Wikipedia entries on Q-SORT-specific topics. This approach allows Q-SORT to tap into the large user base of Wikipedia. The importance of the synergy with Wikipedia, with its >60 million daily readers⁷, cannot be underestimated.

Selected Q-SORT images will also be published also in Wikimedia Commons thanks to the support of [Wikimedia Italia](#); this will also give Wikipedia users the possibility to directly access (and reference in articles) a plethora of significant scientific sources.

- **EFFECT Project**

Dissemination synergies with the [EFFECT Project](#) are important for both communication and dissemination. A cooperation agreement with EFFECT is currently being pursued to this end. From a strategic point of view, dissemination of Q-SORT outcomes among experts reached through EFFECT means that sorter-related technologies developed in Q-SORT might gain further new users across Europe.

- **Other Q-SORT ‘sister’ projects**

Q-SORT will liaise with other sister projects to ensure full and effective collaboration within the FET programme framework and the related flagship initiatives of the European Commission, including the [Quantum Manifesto](#) and [Quantera](#). Moreover, Q-SORT will consolidate its relationship with international projects such as [QEM](#) and the [Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#).

- **External events**

Other important channels of disseminating project results include national networks, European and International workshops, seminars, and conferences organised by other institutions, as well as national and international fairs and exhibitions.

Individual Q-SORT members will attend relevant conferences and sister-project events and disseminate project brochures. Otherwise, Project brochures will be sent for deployment to the event organisers.

- **Scientific papers**

All partners are encouraged to author papers in national and European journals, as well as conference proceedings where partners are invited to present their papers. To this end, many

⁷ Source: <https://analytics.wikimedia.org/dashboards/reportcard/#daily-unique-devices>

Q-SORT deliverables have been conceived as manuscripts for research papers, so as to optimise the time and effort spent doing research.

- **Q-SORT publications**

Printed and online proceedings, in the form of a Book of Abstracts have been and will be produced by WP6 in cooperation with FZJ and CNR-NANO, in order to disseminate the outcomes achieved by the various WPs to a wider public.

- **Q-SORT Events**

These are central to the dissemination and engagement. They consist of:

- a. 3 dedicated Q-SORT International Conferences, scheduled to work in synergy with major conferences held by sister projects and to dovetail with major related conferences;
- b. 9 Interdisciplinary Webinars
- c. 3 Science Bashes
- d. 3 Wikipedia Edit-a-thons
- e. related deployment of specific promotional materials:
 - i. Conference posters;
 - ii. Project brochures.

List of Q-SORT Public Events

Event	Date	Expected Audience	Location	Status
Kick-off Meeting	M1	All partners, European Commission, Civil Society Organisation (E.g. Wikimedia)	Modena - Italy	Done
Q-SORT First international Conference	M8-M12	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Juelich - Germany	Done
Q-SORT Second International Conference	M25-M27	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Erlangen - Germany	Being organised
Q-SORT Third international Conference	M38-M42	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Modena - Italy	To be organised
Q-SORT Science Bashes	M8-M12 / M25-M27 / M38-M42	General Public / Silent Stakeholders / High School Students	Juelich - Germany Erlangen - Germany Modena - Italy	Done Being organised
Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars	M6-M11-M12-M18-M26-M30-M36-M41	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Online Broadcast	3 done
Q-SORT Edit-a-Thons	M8-M12 / M25-M27 / M38-M42	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community General Public / Silent Stakeholders/ High School Students	Juelich - Germany Erlangen - Germany Modena - Italy	Done Being organised To be organised

- Q-SORT Teaser Video and associated Vimeo Channel:** the teaser video and its associated Vimeo channel are geared towards maximising the impact and visibility of Q-SORT. The Web-tailored teaser video will be produced in two versions of different length. It will feature fascinating insights into the physics of the sorter and its possible applications. The visual language employed will be fresh and dynamic, seamlessly merging live action with CGI and, if necessary, miniature work. The video is conceived for a general audience – however, science lovers, high school students, and film buffs will especially appreciate it. The commercials will be mastered in HD; this will be done chiefly in preparation for their Web delivery, but will also afford them the possibility of being integrated into theatrical and broadcast exhibitions if so wished. Lower-definition versions for mobile devices will also be rendered. All IPR associated with the promo will be cleared so as to allow for its free distribution; more precisely, the makers will grant a non-exclusive license to the Q-SORT Consortium, so that the video can be distributed as widely as possible via embedding and - if possible- broadcast and theatrical exhibition. A dedicated Vimeo Channel will be used for all embedding; crucially, this will also provide a set of useful metrics to measure the video’s impact (number of embeds, number of total and partial plays, geographical spread of users, etc.).

4.3.1 SUMMARY OF CHANNELS/ACTIONS

The following table sums up the methods employed by Q-SORT to disseminate its activities and outcomes.

METHOD	PURPOSE	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCES	GUIDELINES FOR PARTNERS
Project website	<i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Communicate</i>	The Project Website is one of the most versatile dissemination tools. It should ‘speak’ to different audiences, using the appropriate linguistic tools.	See D6.1 Q-SORT Project Website . This deliverable describes the website developed for the project, in particular the goals it intends to achieve, the users towards whom it is targeted, the software used, the structure of the public and the reserved areas, the implementation work, the services, the editorial board, the tools for monitoring the website.	Partners are encouraged to send relevant information, news, images to enrich the Project Website and be shared by all.
Partners’ institutional websites	<i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Pages or dedicated pages on these websites are important for the dissemination of the project’s results at a national level and to direct traffic towards the Project Website		Partners are encouraged to publish a page or section describing the project’s activities and results on their institutional websites.
Social networks groups &	<i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i>	All these tools present an opportunity to be proactive and reactive, to share one’s knowledge with the target		Partners are encouraged to follow Q-SORT Social Networks profiles. Partners who manage a professional blog or who

Mailing- lists	<i>Communicate</i>	community, to develop a brand image for Q-SORT and to help spread online word-of-mouth about the progress of research.		are active on social networks are encouraged to promote and disseminate the Project and its results to their own audiences. Partners are encouraged to announce their achievements, publications, etc.
Wikimedia	<i>To:</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Opening up the Wikimedia to experts interested in the topics of Q-SORT.		Partners are encouraged to edit Wikipedia entries and enrich the Wikimedia Commons with images produced during the project.
Press Releases and Newsletters	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Communicate</i>	A press release is a formal announcement to the national press. Partners are encouraged to issue press releases to announce any event or important Q-SORT achievement.	.	Partners should liaise with the Q-SORT coordinator before issuing a press release and to include the Q-SORT logo, e-mail and link to the website.
Brochures and other promotional material	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>communicate</i>	Though communication channels are often electronic, we believe that it is still useful to circulate printed dissemination materials at meetings and events.	The following materials will be available: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Q-SORT Flyer• Q-SORT Poster Dissemination material may be downloaded from a dedicated page in the Project Website. A detailed description of Q-SORT Dissemination material will be provided in <i>D6.6 Printed materials (release 1)</i> . This document will be structured as an easy-to-use internal guide describing dissemination materials that have been completed or will be available in the near future, as well as guidelines on how, where and when to distribute them.	Partners should disseminate Q-SORT promotional material at their professional events. All promotional material will be available for customisation and translation into other languages.
Sister projects and cluster meetings	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i>	Sister projects and cluster meetings are excellent opportunities for	Events archive on Q-SORT website	Partners are advised to use the Project Website and internal mailing lists to inform all partners

	<i>Engage communicate</i>	projects to learn from each other, discuss common issues, and receive feedback on their work. Partners may be asked to give a presentation, participate in a workshop, give a demo, etc. As there may be many projects on the agenda, we encourage partners to make an impact and engage the audience.	Messages circulating in professional mailing list	about professional meetings. Some of Q-SORT's experts could be interested in participating in one of them. Partners are required to always to include the corporate image when presenting or speaking about Q-SORT.
Conference presentations	<i>To: Raise awareness Engage communicate</i>	National and international conferences are an excellent opportunity to share the network's achievements with experts in the field (teaching/ learning, etc).	Events archive on Q-SORT website	Partners are advised to make sure they select conferences where their presentation will have an impact, and will attract the experts they want to speak to. Partners are directed to always use the corporate image when presenting or speaking about Q-SORT. Partners are encouraged to distribute Q-SORT promotional material.
Conference posters	<i>To: Raise awareness</i>	A poster session at a conference may be more appropriate when there is work in progress. Posters may be presented to delegates who attend the session. It may not be as engaging as doing a presentation in the auditorium, but it's an excellent way to attract people and get one-on-one feedback. Often conferences do not foresee calls for papers, but do foresee poster sessions.		Partners are advised to make sure they select conferences where their presentation will have an impact, and will attract the experts they want to speak to. Partners are advised to always include the Q-SORT corporate image. Partners are encouraged to distribute Q-SORT promotional material.

<p>Webinars</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Disseminate</i></p>	<p>Webinars are short workshops that are broadcasted online with a great potential to reach a large audience.</p>		<p>Partners are advised to make to select a topic that will attract the audience they wish to speak to.</p> <p>Partners are advised to always include the corporate image when presenting or speaking about Q-SORT.</p>
<p>Q-SORT Science Bashes</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i></p>	<p>Science Bashes are events that take place in casual settings such as pubs and coffeehouses. They are open to everyone, and feature an engaging conversation with a scientist about a particular topic. Science Bashes represent a grassroots movement. They exist all over the world and can vary from place to place. Venues range from local libraries, to school and coffee houses to neighborhood bars. Even the names of Science Bashes vary, including Science on Tap, Science Pub, Ask a Scientist, and Café Sci.</p>		<p>Partners should provide with topics for the Science Bashes and engage the local communities in these events.</p> <p>Partners will be advised to distribute Q-SORT promotional material on these occasions.</p>
<p>Edit-a-thons</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i></p>	<p>An edit-a-thon is</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a scheduled time where people edit Wikipedia together, whether offline, online, or a mix of both; 2. typically focused on a specific topic, such as science or women's history. 3. a way to recruit new Wikipedians and teach them how to contribute. <p>Edit-a-thons</p>		<p>Partners should provide topics for the edit-a-thons, engage the local communities in these events and to get in touch with the respective national chapter of Wikimedia.</p>

		<p>improve the encyclopedia and can be a great way to help new Wikipedians learn to edit. This is quite different from large conferences such as Wikimania, which often have multiple speakers or panels about a huge variety of topics. An edit-a-thon is also unlike a regular meetup, which tends to be without a single goal and/or for socializing. In other words, an edit-a-thon is like a hackathon for Wikipedians.</p>		
<p>Journal articles and/or Publications</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Disseminate</i></p>	<p>Partners are encouraged at every opportunity to author articles on the Q-SORT project.</p> <p>During the project, partners may wish to contribute to electronic newsletters, blogs, portals.</p> <p>Peer reviewed journals in relevant disciplines will be a very important opportunity once we will have reached an advanced phase of the project, when there are data and results to report.</p>		<p>Partners are advised to frequently include in their work references to the Q-SORT project.</p> <p>Partners must inform and send a copy of any journal article or academic paper to the project's coordinator so that it may be published or mentioned on the Q-SORT website.</p>
<p>Q-SORT Teaser Video</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Communicate</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Raise awareness</i></p>	<p>Q-SORT teaser video is geared towards maximizing the impact and visibility of the Q-SORT project.</p>		<p>Partners should distribute the videos through channels at their disposal, eg: - DVD giveaways - embedding on websites - organizing dedicated broadcast during seminars or conferences.</p>

5 MONITORING AND SUCCESS INDICATORS

The following table lists the updated **success indicators** described in the D1.1 Project Handbook regarding the Project's dissemination, communication, and public engagement efforts.

Indicator No.	Objective/expected result	Indicator name	Expected Progress		
			M12	M30	M42
1	Dissemination and engagement success	Total number of webinars	2	7	9
2	Communication and engagement success	Total number of followers on social networks	500	1000	1500
3	Communication and engagement success	Maximum post reach on social networks	1000	2000	5000
4	Communication success	Number of countries reached through social networks and website	8	16	28
5	Communication and dissemination success	Number of visitors on Project Website (unique IPs)	150	500	750
6	Communication success	Number of views for Project Video	/	1000	2000
7	Communication and dissemination success	Total number of brochures/flyers distributed	4000	8000	12000
8	Dissemination success	Number of conferences attended by Q-SORT staff	12	30	42
9	Dissemination success	Number of papers published	3	5	11
10	Dissemination success	Number of Project Events organised by Q-SORT	1	2	3
11	Dissemination success	Number of participants in the events organised by the Q-SORT	60	120	200
12	Communication and dissemination success	Number of visits to the Q-SORT Website	500	2000	5000

13	Dissemination success	Number of citations of Q-SORT papers	4	14	28
14	Engagement and communication success	Number of quotations or links or embeds of the Q-SORT project (Web, including social networks)	30	100	500
15	Engagement success	Number of Wiki Edit-a-thons	1	2	3
16	Engagement success	Number of Science Bashes	1	2	3
17	Engagement success	Number of 'share' actions on Social Networks	100	200	300
18	Engagement success	Number of items (articles or media) enriched in Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons	10	25	50

The effectiveness of dissemination and engagement activities will be evaluated constantly using the following criteria:

1) Statistical analysis of the Project Website with the following indicators, in order to follow up on users' interest through Website content:

- Page views: number of webpages requested and viewed by the user;
- Visits or sessions: number of visits to the site made by users;
- Unique visitors: number of single users that have visited the site;
- Time spent: time spent in minutes and seconds while navigating or viewing the pages of a site or using a digital application.

[Google Analytics](#) is the main tool to collect fresh insights into how visitors use our site, how they arrived at our site, which parts of our website are performing well, which pages are most popular and how visitors interact with sharing features on the site.

In addition, the Q-SORT social network profiles are managed through [Hootsuite](#), a social media management tool that allows the Q-SORT dissemination team to efficiently track conversations and measure our dissemination campaign results.

Figure 5 The Hootsuite Dashboard - Snapshot

2) Event reporting forms, filled in by partners after each event.

A reporting form has been prepared in order to report on participation in events. This form must be used when a partner is presenting and disseminating Q-SORT-related work at events organised by other institutions. The form template is available in the reserved area of the Project Website: www.qsort.eu/about/reserved-area/

The reports will be analysed in order to ascertain if target groups are reached, and if the definitions of the main target groups need to be adjusted.

Links to the events attended and/or organised by Q-SORT personnel are posted on the Website in the News section as they happen.

Articles about Q-SORT that appear on the Web are monitored on a monthly basis and posted in the News section.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan aims to ensure that:

- the Project overall outreach activities follow the planned schedule and meet with success;
- the messages delivered from the Project to the 'outer world' are coherent and of a high standard;
- the Project maintains a high profile;
- the Project community at large learns from its achievements.

The Project Coordinator, together with the WP6 Leader, will share the strategy developed in this document with all the partners and the WP Leaders, inviting them to contribute ideas for the duration of the project.

Envisioning an overall outreach plan at the beginning of the project ensures that we maximise the impact of dissemination, communication, and public engagement.

In order to make the Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan effective, we have broken it down into a clear and specific set of constituent elements:

Goals: We set out at the beginning the objectives of our dissemination and engagement efforts.

Target Audience and Message: We have identified and described the main target audiences of Q-SORT. For each of the target audiences, we have established the basic elements of the message to be disseminated.

Methods: We have described the media channels and the strategies through which the message of Q-SORT can be best delivered and established a set of clear and simple branding guidelines.

Success: We have listed the metrics to measure success and monitor progress.

ANNEX I: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
European Union	EU
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Social Media	SM
Work Package	WP